

THE OPTIMIZATION OF HUMAN RESOURCES THROUGH VOCATIONAL SCHOOL IN FACING THE DEMOGRAPHIC BONUS

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Abstract

Indonesia will face an era of demographic bonus in the next few years, to be precise from 2030 to 2040. The demographic bonus in question is a period where the population of productive age (15-64 years) is greater than the non-productive age population (65 years and above) with a proportion of more than 60% of the total population of Indonesia. This case happens because of increasing welfare and public education. In welcoming this era, the Government must prepare with careful planning. The government is currently working on various programs to realize the Golden Indonesia Vision 2045. Demographic bonus productive human resources will not be productive if there are no jobs that match the skills and fields they master. The government must prepare various job opportunities and open investment taps both from within the country and abroad. The demographic bonus is a strategic opportunity for Indonesia to accelerate development with the support of abundant human resources (HR) from the productive age. Moreover, in 2030 there is a big agenda for sustainable development (Sustainable Development Goals). In line with this, the government has also launched the Golden Indonesia Vision 2045 with the hope of creating a quality productive generation. The states role is to intervene, creating jobs through investment. So investment, whether using domestic or foreign funds, including inviting foreign capital to enter Indonesia, is actually to create jobs for the productive generation.

Keywords: Demographic Bonus, Vocational School, Sustainable Development Goals, Unemployment.

INTRODUCTION

Comparison of the Number of High School and Vocational School

In general, there are three types of education in Indonesia the academic education, vocational education and professional education. There are similarities in academic, vocational and professional education from the basic level, starting from early childhood education programs, Kindergarten, Elementary School and Middle School. The differences between the two range from high school to college is academic education starts at high school level namely SMA/SMU/MA, then higher education levels from Bachelor's, Master's, to Doctoral degrees. Vocational education starts at high school level namely SMK/MAK, and the higher education level are from D1, D2, D3, D4, Applied Masters and Applied Doctorate. Professional education includes SP1 to SP2.

An important part of the education level is at the senior secondary school (SLTA) level, namely SMA and SMK. At this level there is a transition from children to teenagers to adults or the workforce (productive age) and the transition from school students to college or the world of work. Based on data from the Central Statistics Agency (BPS) in 2023, the number of students at the Senior High School (SMA) level in the country was 5.17 million people. This number increased by 1.44% compared to the previous period which was 5.09 million people. Meanwhile, the number of students at Vocational High School (SMK) level is 5.05 million people. The number decreased by 6.28% compared to 2021/2022 which was 5.39 million people. This data only comes from the Ministry of Education, Culture, Research and Technology (Kemendikbud Ristek). This data does not include the number of students studying at schools managed by the Ministry of Religion (Kemenag). Meanwhile, the number of students that studying under the Ministry of Religion will be 9.17 million in 2022/2023. This number has increased by 1.55% compared to 2021/2022 which was 9.03 million people. For more detailed data on the number of high school and vocational school students can be seen in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Comparison of the number of high school and vocational high school students

These data show that there is an increase in the number of high school students and a decrease in the number of vocational school students. Furthermore, based on data from BPS in 2023 regarding the number of schools, it was found that the number of High School and Vocational High School has increased. The number of High School has increased by 1.63% from 2022 to 2023. Meanwhile, the number of Vocational High School has also increased by 0.46% from 2022 to 2023. Details of the number of High School and Vocational High School can be seen in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Comparison of the number of High School and Vocational High schools

Problems of vocational school graduates

Based on Figure 1 and Figure 2, information is obtained that there has been an increase in the number of students in high schools in accordance with the increase in the number of high schools. Meanwhile at Vocational Schools there has been a decline in the number of students, even though the number of Vocational Schools has increased. Vocational School is a secondary school level that produces graduates who can work in industry or the business world.

Vocational schools are an important part of improving the economy and community welfare in accordance with the mandate of laws and government regulations. Instruction from President of the Republic of Indonesia no. 9 of 2016 concerning Revitalization of Vocational High Schools in the Context of Improving the Quality and Competitiveness of Indonesian Human Resources.

Vocational Schools can produce graduates who become workers needed by the business/industrial world (DU/DI). In reality, the problem that occurs is that there is still high unemployment for vocational school graduates.

BPS data for 2023 explains that the highest open unemployment rate (TPT) is at the vocational and high school levels. Unemployment A comparison of the percentage of unemployed high school and vocational school graduates can be seen in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Comparison of the percentage of open unemployment rates high school and vocational school graduates

Based on Figure 3, information is obtained that the number of unemployed vocational school graduates is still higher than that of high school graduates. Although in 2023 the percentage will both decrease. Vocational school graduates should be immediately absorbed into the world of work, because the curriculum at Vocational Schools has been designed in accordance with existing skill competencies in industry according to the spectrum of the Directorate of Vocational High School Education.

Broadly speaking, there are three problems that occur in vocational schools. Firstly, there is a mismatch between the skill competencies possessed by vocational school students and those required by the business world or world of work. Both vocational schools opened skills competencies in accordance with existing trends, without paying attention to the potential of the area where the school was established. Third, there is a mismatch between vocational school graduates (skill competencies) and the needs of the business and industrial world

Solutions to the problems of vocational school graduates

The match between the competencies of vocational school graduates and the needs of the world of work is an issue that has not been resolved. Changes in skills or competency, technological improvements, global competition are several factors that need to be considered. It is important to synchronize skill competencies in vocational schools with the needs of the world of work. Collaboration between vocational schools and the world of work needs to be strengthened and always go hand in hand.

It is a common sight that people in rural areas or smaller areas will look for work in big cities which provide more job opportunities. This results in an imbalance in the economic levels in rural and urban areas. Many vocational school graduates migrate to the cities that look for works, while the skills competency of graduates in the regions is still below the standard of urban vocational school graduates, so their bargaining value to occupy the same position in the competition is still low. To reduce this problem, one way that can be done is to open skills competencies in vocational schools based on regional potential.

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The establishment of vocational schools with skill competencies needs to pay attention to suitability with regional potential, not just existing trends. If you only follow the trend, vocational school graduates from the regions will be unable to compete with vocational schools in urban areas which are actually favorite and advanced schools. The establishment of a vocational school must look at the potential of each region where the school is established. This is important so that graduates do not have to look for jobs in urban areas, because these areas already have potential and job opportunities that are in accordance with the skills competencies available in vocational schools. By opening a skills competency program based on regional potential, it will be possible to increase the competitiveness of the potential that has been exploited and can increase people's income. What is even better is that vocational school graduates do not need to look for work but can open up job opportunities.

Vocational schools that suit regional potential are a solution to reducing urban sprawl. Vocational schools can produce graduates who suit the job opportunities that exist in the region, so that graduates can be easily absorbed into the world of work and can improve the economy in their respective regions. Graduates who have appropriate skill competencies can become potential workers in increasing the value of local products and regional excellence. So, in the end it can improve community welfare.

Apart from the importance of synchronizing the skills competency programs opened at Vocational Schools with regional potential, there is also the need to determine the location of Vocational Schools. The location of a vocational school is important because it greatly influences the sustainability of the vocational school. Don't let it happen that after the Vocational School is built there are no students because it competes with SMA, MAN and even Vocational Schools which are located nearby while in that location there is only 1 (one) or 2 (two) Junior High Schools (SLTP). The level of accessibility in determining the location of the school is also an important factor to pay attention to, lest people feel that it is difficult to go to school because the vocational school is located far away or requires quite heavy transportation and the lack of public transportation that passes the school.

Based on the description above, it can be understood that, firstly, it is important for us to prepare human resources in facing the Demographic Bonus, one of which is by preparing human resources for vocational school graduates. Synchronization between Skills Competency Programs in Vocational High Schools (SMK) with Regional Potential as a solution to high vocational school unemployment and efforts to increase the competitiveness of products or types of business from existing regional potential and to be able to hold back the rate of urbanization of the productive age. Therefore, it is hoped that in every Provincial Education Office there will be a mapping of vocational schools based on regional potential. This is to capture the need for new vocational schools and provide solutions to increase the competitiveness of production or business based on regional potential while also limiting the flow of urbanization which continues to increase in welcoming the Demographic Bonus.

CONCLUSTION

Members of the Academic Senate and those present at the invitation whom I respect, the explanation above is a series of research that I have carried out and am currently carrying out in an effort to support the Instruction of the President Republic of Indonesia no. 9 of 2016 concerning Revitalization of Vocational High Schools in the Context of Improving the Quality and Competitiveness of Indonesian Human Resources. We need to take this Presidential Instruction deeper because universities are institutions that produce Human Resources which have the burden of carrying out the Government's mandate in facing challenges in the Demographic Bonus era.

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